

1 Levels of radionuclide concentrations in benthic invertebrate species from the Balearic
2 Islands, Western Mediterranean, during the period 2012–2018

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35 **Abstract**

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37 Baseline levels of radionuclides in the marine environment of the Balearic Islands in the
38 Western Mediterranean are non-existent. Because of their ecological role and
39 acknowledged sensitivity to pollutants, the activity concentrations of ^{210}Po , ^{40}K , ^{210}Pb ,
40 ^{90}Sr and ^{234}Th were measured in two types of benthic invertebrates species (mussels and
41 sea urchins) sampled during the period 2012–2018.

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43 The activity concentrations of ^{210}Po ; ^{40}K ; ^{210}Pb and ^{234}Th ranged from 38 ± 1 to 325 ± 11
44 Bq kg^{-1} dry weight (d.w.); 220 ± 10 and $996 \pm 46 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$ d.w.; from ND (lower than the
45 limit of detection) to $55 \pm 8 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$ d.w.; and from ND to $70 \pm 15 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$ d.w.,
46 respectively. In all cases, no artificial ^{90}Sr activity was detected in the collected samples.
47 The committed effective dose to humans was calculated to be in the range from 48 to 640
48 $\mu\text{Sv year}^{-1}$.

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60 Keywords: benthic invertebrates; ^{210}Po ; ^{210}Pb ; ^{90}Sr ; ^{234}Th ; Balearic Islands

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63 There are two well-known sources of radioactivity in the marine environment: ^{40}K and
64 natural decay series of ^{238}U and ^{232}Th ; and man-made radionuclides (^{137}Cs , $^{(239+240)}\text{Pu}$ or
65 ^{90}Sr) (Polykarpov, 1966; Shannon and Cherry, 1967). These chemically-analogue
66 radionuclides of metabolically essential elements are bioaccumulated in tissues of the
67 marine species through different mechanisms (Carvalho, 2018). Therefore, these
68 radionuclides are introduced into the food chain via ingestion of marine food. In order to
69 evaluate intake of radionuclides by human, an assessment of radionuclide concentrations
70 in marine organisms must be carried out. The dose to the body (the energy absorbed from
71 internal irradiation due to ingestion of radionuclides) produces biological effects in
72 humans. An exhaustive radiation dose assessment establishes a baseline that is useful to
73 control any increase due to nuclear accidents or industrial activities (Feroz Khan et al.,
74 2014).

75

76 Artificial radionuclides are mainly released in the environment by Nuclear power plant
77 (NPP) accidents (Chernobyl in 1986, or Fukushima Daiichi NPP in 2011), and nuclear
78 weapon tests (during the 1960s) (Fathivand and Amidi, 2007). Among the artificial
79 radionuclides, ^{90}Sr is considered a key radionuclide to be controlled (Castrillejo et al.,
80 2016). ^{90}Sr is a primary fission product (Habibi et al., 2015) with a long biological (13
81 years) and nuclear half-life (28.9 years) that persists in the environment for a long time.
82 Furthermore, ^{90}Sr is a chemical analogue of calcium metabolizing in tissues with high
83 calcium content, such as bones, and consequently strontium is one of the most hazardous
84 radionuclides.

85

86 Concerning natural radionuclides, ^{238}U decay chain includes ^{210}Po , ^{210}Pb , and ^{234}Th . The
87 main sources of ^{210}Po ($T_{1/2} = 138$ days) and ^{210}Pb ($T_{1/2} = 22.3$ years) in the environment

88 are: dry and wet fallout of emanated ^{222}Rn from the earth's crust to the atmosphere
89 (Baskaran, 2011), radioactive decay of ^{226}Ra dissolved in seawater (Bacon et al., 1976;
90 Carvalho and Fowler, 1993), and waste discharges from industries processing
91 technologically enhanced naturally occurring radioactive materials (TENORM)
92 (Carvalho et al., 2010; Villa et al., 2009).

93
94 ^{210}Po is a toxic element that releases locally the radiation dose through its alpha-particle
95 decay of 5.3 MeV originating a fatal damage to different organs and tissues (Stewart et
96 al., 2008). It is the major contributor to radiation dose received by humans in sea food,
97 such as fish, crustaceans and molluscs (Dahlgard, 1996; Wildgust et al., 2000). On the
98 other hand, ^{210}Pb is a beta emitter and the second highest radiotoxic radionuclide in the
99 natural decay chain (Štok and Smodiš, 2011). Regarding ^{234}Th , it is a natural
100 radionuclide with a half-life of 24.1 days. The radioactive levels of ^{234}Th have been
101 published by previous studies in plankton (Marsh and Buddemeier, 1984; Paschoa et al.,
102 1981). However, few studies have been carried out on bioaccumulation of ^{234}Th in marine
103 organisms in the higher trophic levels (Ishikawa et al., 2004).

104
105 Finally, natural ^{40}K has a very long half-life ($T_{1/2} = 1.251 \times 10^9$ years) and the reported
106 activity concentrations represent the natural background levels for marine organisms
107 (Meli et al., 2008). The dose produced by ^{40}K is due to its beta emission and it is negligible
108 compared to the radiation dose associated to ^{210}Po (UNSCEAR, 2008).

109
110 Of all marine species, benthic invertebrates have been widely utilized as bioindicators for
111 assessing the contamination and ecotoxicology taking place in the marine environment
112 (Carvalho et al., 2010; Fonollosa et al., 2017; Francioni et al., 2007; Kiliç et al., 2014;
113 Rožmarić et al., 2012; Thébault et al., 2008; Topcuoğlu et al., 2003; Uğur et al., 2011).

114

115 As far as we known, there are no previous studies on radioactive pollution in the Balearic
116 Islands in the Western Mediterranean. In view of this fact, the main objectives of this
117 study are (1) to assess the activity concentration of ^{210}Po , ^{40}K , ^{210}Pb , ^{90}Sr and ^{234}Th in two
118 types of benthic invertebrates distributed in the Balearic Islands, and (2) to estimate the
119 annual effective ingestion dose to human population due to seafood consumption.

120

121 Samples were collected at two sampling locations around the Balearic Islands (Western
122 Mediterranean), specifically at Menorca Island (BAL1/01 and BAL1/02) (see Fig. 1). The
123 BAL 1/01 location was at the Port of Mahon, near to the city of approximately 28,000
124 inhabitants. The collection sites are aquaculture zones of marine invertebrates.
125 Radioactivity levels were determined in two commercial invertebrate species regularly
126 sold in the domestic markets. The studied species included one mollusc bivalve species
127 (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) and one sea-urchin ecninoderm (*Paracentrotus lividus*). The
128 mussels were not native to Balearic Islands, they were transplanted in autumn from Ebro
129 Delta or Adriatic Sea regions.

130

131 Fig. 1. Map showing the study area and sampling stations.

132

133 Samples were collected from 2012 to 2018 at the two locations. The life cycle of the
 134 invertebrate species and the commercial extraction periods established the sampling dates
 135 (Table 1).

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139 Table 1. Sampling locations and period.

Location	Specie	Coordinates	Sampling period
Puerto de Mahón (BAL 1/01)	<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>	39° 53.65'N–04° 16.10'E	2012–2018
Costa Este Menorca (BAL 1/02)	<i>Paracentrotus lividus</i>	39° 52.40'N–04° 18.38'E	2012–2017

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142 Adult specimens of the same species per sampling year were pooled together in order to
143 obtain at least, 100 g of dry weight to carry out the analytical methods. At least, 1,000 g
144 of wet flesh of each species were treated for each sampling year.

145

146 In the laboratory, the invertebrate samples were washed with distilled water in order to
147 remove the attached sand/silt. Then, their soft tissues were dissected, weighted, frozen at
148 -20 °C, and freeze-dried for 24 h. Finally the dehydrated samples were weighted, crushed
149 and homogenized.

150

151 To determine ^{210}Po activity concentration, a known activity of internal tracer ^{209}Po was
152 added to the lyophilized sample in order to calculate the analytical recovery. First,
153 samples were digested with concentrated HNO_3 and H_2O_2 during 24 h at low temperature
154 (<25 °C) in order to avoid foam formation. The obtained solution was then digested at
155 high temperature (<80 °C) and slowly evaporated to near dryness on a hot plate. The
156 obtained residue was dissolved again 2 or 3 times with concentrated HNO_3 and H_2O_2 to
157 destroy all the organic material. Finally, the residue was dissolved in 100 mL of 1 M HCl
158 and filtered through a 0.45 μm pore filter. About 0.1 g of ascorbic acid salt was added to
159 the solution as a reducing agent. A silver disc was introduced into the solution
160 continuously stirred for 4 h at 85-90 °C and pH 1.5–2.0 being ^{210}Po spontaneously plated
161 onto the disc. The disc was then removed, washed with distilled water and acetone, and
162 dried. An alpha-spectrometry instrument (Alpha Analyst, Canberra) containing a
163 Passivated Implanted Planar Silicon (PIPS) detector was used for counting the disc. Alpha
164 spectrum analysis was performed using Alpha Analyst software taking into account the
165 decay corrections for ^{210}Po and ^{209}Po activities obtaining high chemical yields (>70%)
166 (Hurtado-Bermudez et al., 2017).

167

168 The radioanalytical method accuracy was validated by the analysis of certified reference
169 materials (CRM) provided by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA-437,
170 IAEA-330 and IAEA-414). It was observed that obtained values were in good agreement
171 with the recommended values.

172

173 Regarding gamma-ray emitting radionuclides, lyophilized samples were sealed into 80
174 mL cylindrical beakers and were allowed to elapse at least 4 weeks before counting to
175 reach secular equilibrium between ^{226}Ra and their daughters (^{214}Pb and ^{214}Bi). Samples
176 were counted for 1–3 days using a low-background Canberra HPGe GR-6022 detector
177 with 60% relative efficiency, surrounded by a 10 cm thick high-purity lead shield. The
178 absolute efficiencies of the detectors were calculated using Canberra LabSOCS software
179 taking into account the effect of self-attenuation of low energy gamma-rays within the
180 sample (Hurtado and Villa, 2010). The spectra were analyzed using Canberra Genie 2000
181 gamma software v3.2. ^{210}Pb activity concentration was calculated by 46.5 keV gamma
182 emission, ^{226}Ra activity concentration was obtained through 295 and 351 keV gamma-
183 rays emitted by ^{214}Pb . ^{40}K was estimated using 1460.8 keV gamma emission. ^{234}Th
184 activity concentration was assessed by analyzing the 63.3 keV gamma-ray. Each
185 uncertainty of activity concentration covered one sigma counting statistics.

186

187 The validation of the gamma-ray spectrometry analyses was carried out through the
188 successful participation on several intercomparison exercises organized by ICRM on
189 efficiency calibration and coincidence-summing correction (Lépy et al., 2012; Vidmar et
190 al., 2008).

191

192 ^{90}Sr activity concentration was determined by measuring its daughter ^{90}Y in secular
193 equilibrium (Rivera-Silva et al., 2019). Samples were dried and ashed at 610°C to remove

194 organic materials, and then 1 to 3 g of ashes were used for the analysis. About 20 mg of
195 Y carrier (Y_2O_3) was added to the ashes and then dissolved in 60 mL of 1 M HCl. Then,
196 pH value was adjusted to 1.2, by the addition of 2 g of citric and ascorbic acid and, finally,
197 it was transferred into a separation funnel containing 60 mL of 5% HDEHP in toluene.
198 After shaking for 5 minutes, the Sr/Y were separated whereas Y remained in the organic
199 phase. Y was back-extracted from HDEHP by shaking for 1 minute with 60 mL 0.08 M
200 HCl, and then 50 mL 3 M HCl. Yttrium was precipitated in the aqueous phase at pH to
201 9-10 as $Y(OH)_3$. Then, it was dissolved in 1 mL of 65% HNO_3 , and transferred into a
202 plastic scintillation vial containing 19 mL of distilled water. The ^{90}Y activity was
203 immediately measured in an ultralow background liquid scintillation spectrometer,
204 Quantulus 1220TM (PerkinElmer, Inc.) through Cerenkov counting. The spectra were
205 acquired and analyzed by WinQ and EASYView software. After the measurement, the
206 recovery yield was obtained by complexometric titration of Y with EDTA.

207

208 The radioanalytical method accuracy was validated by the analysis of certified reference
209 materials (CRM) provided by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA-473,
210 IAEA-330 and IAEA-384). The obtained values were in good agreement with the
211 recommended values.

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213 Activity concentrations of ^{90}Sr , ^{210}Po ; ^{40}K ; ^{210}Pb and ^{234}Th in benthic invertebrate
214 samples in the sampling sites and for each sampling campaign are presented in Table 2.

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222 Table 2.

223 Activity concentrations of radionuclides (Bq/kg d.w.), their corresponding uncertainties

224 (u), and annual ingestion dose for invertebrate samples in the study areas during the

225 sampling campaigns

Station	Date	Season	Specie	²¹⁰ Po (Bq/kg)	u	²¹⁰ Pb (Bq/kg)	u	²³⁴ Th (Bq/kg)	u	⁴⁰ K (Bq/kg)	u	⁹⁰ Sr (Bq/kg)	dose (μSv/year)
BAL1/01	26/7/12	summer	Mussel	206	7	13	2	10	3	357	18	< 1.9	201
BAL1/01	9/12/12	autumn	Mussel	123	4	29	3	20	5	427	22	< 1.9	133
BAL1/01	17/12/13	autumn	Mussel	108	4	12	2	42	9	332	12	<1.6	102
BAL1/01	28/12/14	winter	Mussel	208	11	12	5	< 9		262	17	< 3	640
BAL1/01	15/12/15	autumn	Mussel	254	9	35	10	31	12	438	24	< 9.1	233
BAL1/01	12/12/16	autumn	Mussel	146.4	4.9	< 10		< 8		395	32	< 2.7	145
BAL1/01	24/4/17	spring	Mussel	325	11	18	6	27	9	352	19	< 2	240
BAL1/01	12/12/18	autumn	Mussel	218	7.4	11.4	4.2	< 9		376	25	< 2	209
BAL1/02	26/7/12	summer	Sea urchin	38	1	6	1	27	5	364	16	< 1.7	48
BAL1/02	17/12/13	autumn	Sea urchin	50	2	21	1	60	12	220	10	< 1.7	93
BAL1/02	22/4/14	spring	Sea urchin	42	2	22	4	55	11	291	16	< 1.6	83
BAL1/02	6/4/15	spring	Sea urchin	56	2	< 10		70	15	272	12	< 1.9	85
BAL1/02	12/12/16	autumn	Sea urchin	56.4	1.9	55	8	48	10	996	46	< 2.1	111
BAL1/02	11/12/17	autumn	Sea urchin	61.5	5.1	15.4	4.2	41.2	12.7	396	42	< 1	51

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229 The activity concentrations of ²¹⁰Po were in the range from 108 ± 4 to 325 ± 11 Bq kg⁻¹

230 d.w. for mussels; and from 38 ± 1 to 61.5 ± 5.1 Bq kg⁻¹ d.w. for sea urchin. The highest

231 ²¹⁰Po activity concentration was found in mussels and sea urchin during 2017 sampling

232 campaign. The lowest activities were determined in the samples from 2012 to 2013 for

233 sea-urchins and mussels respectively.

234

235 The highest activity concentrations of ²¹⁰Po in the species were found in mussels (Table

236 2). All bivalves (*M. galloprovincialis*) in our study presented higher ²¹⁰Po contents than

237 the sea-urchin (*P. lividus*), which presented the lowest ²¹⁰Po activity concentrations

238 (Table 2). Statistically significant differences were found between the species (ANOVA,

239 $p < 0.001$). These findings may be explained by four factors: (a) the relative position of
240 the species within the marine food chain, (b) the organism's polonium elimination
241 mechanisms, (c) the characteristics of the particles the organisms feed on, and (d) the
242 differences between the sampling sites BAL 1/01 and BAL 1/02. Therefore, the increase
243 of ^{210}Po activity contents at each trophic level seems to partly explain the differences
244 between *M. galloprovincialis* (filter feeder) and *P. lividus* (herbivore grazer and into a
245 lower position in the food chain) (Fowler, 2011). Moreover, mussels feed on suspended
246 material what is intrinsically more associated to polonium uptake. Additionally, the
247 behavior of ^{210}Po in both species was similar to that of persistent organic pollutants
248 (POPs) such as polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) in the sampling area (Deudero et al.,
249 2007). This fact may be due to the lipid solubility and the absence of adequate metabolic
250 pathways in organisms accumulating both ^{210}Po and PCBs in fatty tissues (Ambrosio et
251 al., 2018). Moreover, the nearest geographical area in the western Mediterranean with
252 available ^{210}Po data for mussels is the Ebro Delta ($813.0 \pm 72.9 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$). Our results in
253 *M. galloprovincialis* samples are lower than those reported in Ebro Delta probably due to
254 the fact that the Ebro Delta is a highly industrialized area (Fonollosa et al., 2017).

255

256 On the other hand, there was an overall average decrease of the ^{210}Po activity
257 concentrations for bivalve molluscs samples in 2013 and 2016 (see Fig. 2). Probably,
258 some environmental parameters changed, such as the amount of suspended particulate
259 matter or plankton what involved lower values for activity concentrations of ^{210}Po in
260 bivalve molluscs, either the bivalve molluscs were originated from different areas before
261 being transplanted. The values for activity concentrations of ^{210}Po in sea urchin *P. lividus*
262 present a constant and low value around $50 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1} \text{ d.w.}$ (see Fig. 3).

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266 Fig. 2. Activity concentrations of different radionuclides ($\text{Bq kg}^{-1} \text{ dw}$) in benthic
 267 invertebrates in BAL 1/01 sampling site from 2012 to 2018

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269 The concentration of ^{210}Pb in mussels ranged from ND (not detected or below Minimum
 270 Detectable Activity) to $35 \pm 10 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1} \text{ d.w.}$ in 2015, and from ND to $55 \pm 8 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$
 271 d.w. in 2016 for sea urchin. No statistically significant difference was found between the
 272 species (ANOVA, $p > 0.05$). ^{210}Pb activity concentrations were relatively low probably
 273 due to the fact that ^{210}Po is mainly associated to the cytoplasm of the cells and it is
 274 subsequently assimilated into the internal tissues of the organisms ingesting these cells.
 275 On the other hand, particle reactive nuclides like ^{210}Pb and ^{234}Th are mainly bind to the
 276 surface membrane of the cell becoming poorly assimilated by the grazer organism
 277 (Stewart et al., 2008).

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281 Fig. 3. Activity concentrations of different radionuclides (Bq kg^{-1} d.w.) in benthic
 282 invertebrates in BAL 1/02 sampling site from 2012 to 2017

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284 ^{210}Po and ^{210}Pb activity concentrations measured in this study are similar to the values
 285 reported in the literature (see Table 3). In this study, the $^{210}\text{Po}/^{210}\text{Pb}$ ratio was found to be
 286 in the range from 4 to 19 with a mean value of 13, being the ^{210}Po activity in the bivalves
 287 unsupported. The range of $^{210}\text{Po}/^{210}\text{Pb}$ ratio is similar to those reported by several studies
 288 (see Table 3). The $^{210}\text{Po}/^{210}\text{Pb}$ ratios in sea urchin samples were much lower ranging from
 289 1 to 6 with a mean value of 3.

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298 Table 3. ^{210}Po and ^{210}Pb activity concentrations, $^{210}\text{Po}/^{210}\text{Pb}$ ratio, and annual effective
 299 ingestion dose (E_d) expressed in microsievert per year ($\mu\text{Sv year}^{-1}$), in bivalves reported
 300 by other authors.

301

References	Country	^{210}Po (Bq kg ⁻¹ d.w.)	^{210}Pb (Bq kg ⁻¹ d.w.)	$^{210}\text{Po}/^{210}\text{Pb}$	E_d ($\mu\text{Sv year}^{-1}$)
(McDonald et al., 1996)	UK	103–3124	-	-	-
(Uğur et al., 2002)	Turkey	52–1344	6–167	3–25	-
(Desideri et al., 2011)	Italy	75–223	2–25	4–62	96–466
(Carvalho et al., 2011)	Portugal	102–759	2.6–45	18–51	-
(Charmasson et al., 2011)	France	203	20	10–15	-
(Uğur et al., 2011)	Turkey	53–1960	6–135	4–137	-
(Štok and Smodiš, 2011)	Slovenia	51–106	2.7–3.0	17–111	8.5
(Rožmarić et al., 2012)	Croatia	22–207	2.8–9.3	6–31	53–497
(Kiliç et al., 2014)	Turkey	26–280	1–23	8–24	0.2–3.3
(Kim et al., 2017)	Korea	240	-	-	19–189
(Fonollosa et al., 2017)	Spain	263–813	3.4–5.4	49–241	100.8
(Hurtado-Bermúdez et al., 2018)	Spain	40–506	17–92	4–16	41–479
This work	Spain	108–325	35	4–19	102–640

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304 ^{40}K in bivalves ranged from 262 to 438 Bq kg⁻¹ d.w., and they are similar than the global
 305 average value (420 Bq kg⁻¹) (UNSCEAR, 2008). The activity concentration in sea urchin
 306 for ^{40}K ranged from 220 to 996 Bq kg⁻¹ d.w., achieving the highest value in 2016 due
 307 probably due to port activity either fishermen or tourism. Regarding ^{234}Th radionuclide,
 308 its activity concentrations ranged were in the range from 10 to 42 Bq kg⁻¹ d.w., and from
 309 27 to 70 Bq kg⁻¹ d.w. for mussels and sea urchin, respectively. Statistically significant
 310 differences were found between the species (ANOVA, $p < 0.005$). These values are
 311 comparable to those reported in the only two published studies involving ^{234}Th values in
 312 marine biota (Hurtado-Bermúdez et al., 2019; Ishikawa et al., 2004).

313

314 Finally, ^{90}Sr activity was not detected in any of the analyzed samples. Probably, ^{90}Sr has
315 reached levels lower than limit of detection being unavailable for uptake into the food
316 chain indicating that fallout ^{90}Sr may have bounded in soils or sediments. It may also
317 occur that the detection limit of the technique (higher than 1 Bq kg^{-1}) is not low enough
318 to measure the expected concentrations (0.8 Bq kg^{-1}) in the area (Nonova and Tosheva,
319 2016).

320

321 Many benthic invertebrates are consumed in the Mediterranean diet. Therefore, it is
322 essential to evaluate the radiation dose due to the consumption of seafood. Annual
323 ingestion doses, as a result of the consumption of benthic invertebrates, were calculated
324 for adults using the following equation (IAEA, 2014):

325

$$326 \quad E_d = A \times m \times C_f \quad (6)$$

327

328 where E_d (Sv) is the annual effective ingestion dose, A is the activity concentration (Bq
329 kg^{-1} w.w.) in the sample, m (kg) is the estimation of annual intake of seafood, and C_f is
330 the dose coefficient for adults (Sv Bq^{-1}). The annual intake of seafood was obtained from
331 the database of food consumption maintained by the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture,
332 Food and Environment ($m = 4.5 \text{ kg}$ of wet tissue per year per capita). The values of the
333 dose coefficients used for ^{210}Po , ^{210}Pb , ^{40}K and ^{234}Th were $1.26 \cdot 10^{-6}$, $6.90 \cdot 10^{-7}$, $6.20 \cdot 10^{-9}$,
334 $3.40 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ Sv/Bq}$, respectively (IAEA, 2014).

335

336 The annual effective doses, resulting from the ingestion of ^{210}Po , ^{210}Pb , ^{40}K and ^{234}Th
337 through the consumption of the seafood samples analyzed in this study, are shown in

338 Table 2. The obtained values were in range from 102-640 $\mu\text{Sv}/\text{year}$ to 48-111 $\mu\text{Sv}/\text{year}$
339 for mussels and sea urchin, respectively. The annual ingestion doses, calculated for the
340 analyzed mussels, are similar to those reported in other studies (see Table 3), and are
341 within the interval of ingestion dose due to natural radiation (200–1000 $\mu\text{Sv}/\text{year}$)
342 (UNSCEAR, 2011). However, the annual effective ingestion dose strongly depends on
343 the annual intake of seafood via diet. This fact should be taken into account when
344 comparing annual effective doses between different regions or countries.

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